

Consultancy to design and PoC a platform for monitoring live indicators to measure EOSC readiness within MS/AC

Final report

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Introduction

This report describes the work carried out in the period between March and September 2021, more precisely from 25th March 2021 and 15th of September.

The aim of the consultancy was to develop a Proof of Concept (PoC) for a platform monitoring live indicators in relation to EOSC readiness at member states (MS) associated countries (AC) level.

The need for this consultancy emerged from the work carried out by the INFRAEOSC5 Landscaping Task Force who developed a set of indicators to assess EOSC readiness within MS/ACs. During the work, the request of moving from a static view of landscaping to monitoring a living set of indicators emerged as a way to allow assessing the MS/AC progresses towards the implementation of the EOSC vision and identifying success stories and areas of improvement on which they could intervene.

The overall aim of the consultancy was, therefore, to validate the possibility of developing a dashboard solution that will minimise the effort needed to collect the information, also by harvesting information from trusted open data sources automatically and, where needed, manually, and facilitate the semi-automated evaluation of EOSC readiness against indicators within the MS/AC.

More precisely the objectives of the consultancy were as follows:

- Use the initial list of indicators and related metrics defined by the Landscape Task Force, and reuse relevant outcomes produced by INFRAEOSC-5b and predecessor projects.
- Design the dashboard and select an appropriate tool to implement it. Define the workflows for the automatic and non-automatic data collection.
- Define processes for practically implementing the active monitoring, reporting and analysis of progress against the indicators, including user guidelines.
- Define mechanisms to ensure the transparency, accountability and actionability of the collected information.
- Ensure flexible solutions to update and develop new indicators.
- Involve beta testers among the NOSCIs/Mandated Organizations to test and tune the proposed solutions.
- Arrange a virtual Validation Workshop to present the work done and collect additional feedback to consolidate the PoC results.
- Provide an estimate of the effort and any other requirements (e.g. software compliance with standards) needed to implement the monitoring on an annual basis at the country level.

The use and customisation of an Open-Source tool, with the consequent release of all developed software under an Open Source license was encouraged.

1. Activities carried out

In this section we briefly report the activities carried out that can be aggregated in three main typologies:

- analysis of EOSC readiness indicators, data source and data availability
- co-design and testing activities
- PoC technical development

1.1 Analysis of EOSC readiness indicators, data source and data availability

The work started by analysing the list of indicators developed by the Landscaping taskforce and accessing the availability of reliable data at European level, possibly in open data standards so to be ingested automatically by the platform. *Unfortunately, none of the indicators prove to be ready-to-use data at EU level, apart from the indicator “OS/FAIR policies supported/monitored/planned - national”* that can be linked to a descriptive information available on the EOSC portal (<https://eosc-portal.eu/policy/EU-Countries>). However, this descriptive information on national policies do not allow a straightforward analysis of the policies or a comparison among countries, but it is nevertheless useful for contextualizing the situation in the various MS in a qualitative way. Indeed, this source has been used in this perspective.

The analysis has been carried out by analysing online datasets and carrying out meetings and exchanging emails with experts belonging to the EOSC community. More specifically, in this first phase, we consulted with the Landscaping taskforce members, with the responsible persons of the Italian catalogue of EOSC, with the OpenAIRE Italian NOAD coordinator and ICDI Competence Centre Coordinator and mail exchanges have happened with EOSC portal contact person and responsible persons of Zenodo.

Then the analysis moved from the European level to the national level focusing on the four countries initially selected as case studies: Italy, Portugal, Slovenia, and Bosnia. Dedicated one to one online meetings were organised with national representatives (belonging to the Landscaping taskforce) for presenting the PoC alfa version (see section 1.2) and analysing data availability at country level. A fifth case study, France, was added in the later stage of the project to enlarge the analysis and a dedicated questionnaire for evaluating data availability was developed and sent to country representatives. The figure that follows shows data availability for the considered countries. The colour code is as follows: green when the data is available in open data format or not, orange when the data is partially available (need to consider different sources, not exactly matching the indicator and similar), red when the information is not available at all. White when we were not able to gather information on data availability for a specific indicator.

Data availability is not equally available in the analysed countries and, even when the data are available (green colour) very often they are not in open formats, but can be inserted manually as the data are available at country level in some form (reports, online pages). Moreover, data on policies are particularly difficult to obtain in a comparable way.

Indicator	Country 1	Country 2	Country 3	Country 4	Country 5
Proposed Readiness indicators for Architecture					
A. National (regional) registry or other federation mechanisms for data in place/planned.	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
a1. Number of enrolled services	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red
a2. Number of searches	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red
a.3 number of SLAs available	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red
B. National (regional) dataset catalogue(s) in place/planned	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green
b1. Number of enrolled datasets	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red
b2. Number of searches	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green
b3. Integration with other data catalogues	Green	Red	Green	Orange	Green
Proposed readiness indicators for Organisation and Governance					
A. National Initiatives in place/planned etc.	Green	Orange	Orange	Green	Green
a1. Funding - structural, internal, per project	Green	Red	Orange	Red	Green
a2. Funding plans	Green	Red	Orange	Red	Orange
a3. Stakeholders involved (number, type)	Green	Red	Red	Red	Orange
B. Strategic roadmap (IR, OS, etc?)	Green	Green	Red	Green	Orange
C. Specific funding programmes for OS/EOSC data science?	Orange	Orange	Red	Orange	Green
Proposed readiness indicators for Policies					
A. OS/FAIR policies supported/monitored/planned	Green	Green	Red	Orange	Orange
a1. National	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green
a2. At the organisational level	Green	Orange	Red	Red	Green
a3. Mandatory/formal/informal	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red
a4. Funding constraints	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red
a5. Incentives	Green	Red	Orange	Orange	Red
B. DM policies in e/supported/monitored/planned					
b1. National	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green
b2. At the organisational level	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red
b3. Mandatory/formal/informal	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red
b4. Funding constraints	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red
b5. Incentives	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red

Proposed readiness indicators for Infrastructure					
A. Resources					
a1. Number of CPUs					
a2. Storage capacity					
a3. Infrastructure availability 7/24					
a4. Helpdesk support 7/24					
a5. Availability of certain types of infrastructure services to researchers (HPC, storage, HTC, GPUs, remote access to science facilities)					
B. Number of infrastructure users (individuals , organisations)					
C. National NREN delegates security and user management policies					
D. National IdP exists?					
E. Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs)					
Proposed readiness indicators for Training & Skills					
A. National/regional curricula in place/planned (compliance with international?)					
a1. Data scientists					
a2. Data stewards					
a3. How many university courses? How many graduates?					
B. Basic training available for researchers & research support staff					
b1. National competence centres					
b2. Certification of competences?					
C. Number of trained people per year					

Fig. 1 Data availability in Italy, Portugal, Slovenia, Bosnia and France. Countries have been renamed with numbers to avoid comparisons among countries as this was not the scope of our analysis.

1.2 Co-design and testing: activities and results

We carried out 3 co-design workshops that helped in:

- better define the scope of the Dashboard
- mapping the technical and non-technical requirements of the community
- define personas
- select the most suitable indicators to be used for contextualising the countries' performances.

The dashboard goals were defined as follows:

- Access information
 - have an up-to-date mapping of the situation at country level
 - map trends and progresses over time
- Learn
 - support reciprocal learning among countries thanks to data but also with success stories and recommendations based on the data
- Take action
 - have data that support "lobbying" for investments at country level

It clearly emerged that *the dashboard should not be a toll for ranking countries' performances* and that data trustworthiness is a crucial issue that, as we will see, emerged also in the final validation workshop as key.

Here below a visual summary of the main results in terms of technical and non-technical requirements.

Requirements gathering and validation

Fig. 2 Requirements gathered during the co-design workshops

With reference to the development of personas, it emerged that the primary users of the dashboard would be:

- Policy makers at national (ministries, regions, federals, dean with mandate on open

- science to help them with decisions on internal policies) and EU level
- Mandate organizations: could be some of the most frequent users of the dashboard. They have similar motivation as decision makers but different perspectives. Indeed, they want to assess if a given strategy is working in a coherent way, look for success stories and areas to be improved

They need to access trustable, comparable, and updated data, reuse them (also for defining success cases and evaluate policies) and update them as needed.

The dashboard for them needs to be easy to not create frustration, complete and easy to read even at a first glance.

Incomplete data could create frustration, all materials should be up-to-date and there should be a disclaimer about data ingestion., for example information on who entered the data, using what source and when the data were uploaded.

Secondary users would be:

- Researchers
- The press
- National OS cloud initiatives
- Discipline communities

While journalists will need clear and reusable information (like a few infographics summarizing the main information) with contextual information, national OS cloud initiatives and discipline communities will have similar needs of those of the primarily users. Additionally, researchers will need to download data, quote them and re-use them as needed.

In the first co-design workshop it also emerged the necessity to add to the PoC dedicated country pages showing contextual information. Therefore, a list of indicators, with related, agreed, data sources was developed and improved in following meetings. The agreed indicators, included in the final version of the PoC, are the following:

Demographic			
Population on 1 January by age and sex	Number of inhabitants	Eurostat	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/demo_pjan/default/table?lang=en
Human capital in the research sectors			
Population having completed tertiary education age 15-64	Population with tertiary education	Eurostat	https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=edat_lfse_03&lang=en
Graduates at doctoral level by sex and age groups - per 1000 of population aged 25-34	Graduated at doctoral level - per 1000 of population aged 25-34	Eurostat	https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=educ_uae_grad06&lang=en

Share of R&D personnel and researchers in total active population	R&D personnel and researchers	Eurostat	https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=rd_p_perslf&lang=en
Funding in education and R&D			
Expenditure on education as % of GDP	Expenditure on education as % of GDP	Eurostat	https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=educ_figdp&lang=en
R&D expenditure per country	Share of government budget allocated to R&D	Eurostat	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/gba_nabste/default/table?lang=en
Digital Landscape			
Connectivity	Connectivity	DESI	https://digital-agenda-data.eu/datasets/desi/indicators
Use of Internet Services	Use of Internet Services	DESI	https://digital-agenda-data.eu/datasets/desi/indicators
Digital Public Services	Digital Public Services	DESI	https://digital-agenda-data.eu/datasets/desi/indicators
OS policies			
Qualitative description of the OS policies at national level	Further information on the OS situation in the country	OpenAire	https://eosc-portal.eu/policy/EU-Countries

Tab. 1 Contextual indicators and related data sources

Other requirements emerged during the co-design process include:

- In evaluating the usage of some services, it is important to consider the size of the scientific community of reference. Indeed, some services are for small disciplinary communities but could be crucial to them, while other are more general in nature so it is normal to expect higher number of users.
- For entering data manually, a template or a questionnaire-like interphase is desirable.
- It is important to include a threshold for EOSC readiness; at the present stage it is not possible to define “when a country is EOSC mature” but it is important that the platform allow such kind of analysis.
- The dashboard needs to be flexible and allow to add and delete indicators and related sources, however, indicators should not be changed too often otherwise it will be impossible to measure progresses over time.

Besides the co-design workshops, the PoC have been presented several times at the landscaping workshop meetings, which were additional occasions to gather feedback from participants and further develop the PoC. Also, the EOSC symposium (June 2021) was an occasion to gather feedback and expectations from the EOSC enlarged community. Email

exchanges with task force members and other stakeholders also helped in analysing data sources, data availability and in refining requirements.

With reference to testing, six countries were invited, and accepted, to act as testers: Portugal, Slovenia, Serbia, Italia, France and Finland. It was decided to enlarge the number of countries considered (from 5 to 6) so to better gather more feedback, also from countries that were not engaged in the co-design phase (France and Finland) and where, in some sense, more “external” to the PoC.

Representatives of the above-mentioned countries were granted access to the platform with dedicated usernames and passwords. Instructions on how to navigate the platform and upload dataset were provided too. After using the platform for half an hour or so (this was our request), they replied to a short questionnaire and the results of the testing are as follows.

Overall, the experience with the dashboard was considered satisfactory and the dashboard itself easy to use. Only one person, indeed, found it confusing. One respondent suggested some improvement in the visualisation: “The interface is very clear, but on smaller screens some diagrams are quite illegible as country codes tend to overlap. The function of the inspector (top left in diagrams) and download (bottom right) buttons is not clear. It would be good to include some textual explanations on the Ingestion page.”

The logic”, the structure (ingestion, monitoring, visualisation) of the dashboard resulted clear or very clear to most of the respondents.

Then, we asked to rate, attributing a value from 1 to 5 where 1 is “not difficult at all” and 5 is “very difficult” the main functionalities of the dashboard: the figure below shows the results obtained.

Fig. 3 Test results on main dashboard's functionalities

Overall, the dashboard appears to be easy in all its main aspects/features for most respondents. Log-in, monitoring the upload status of the files and selecting datasets seems to be very easy for most respondents while understanding the situation at EU and country level in the visualisation pages appear less straightforward. Very probably this is related to the quantity of data available in the pages (still very limited) more than to the technical aspects on those pages.

Uploading a dataset appears an easy task too for those that carry it out (one respondent didn't so that the number of respondents for that question is lower than for the others).

Finally, we asked to mention what was appreciated in the dashboard and what could be improved. Generally, the comments were positive, and the ease of usage was particularly appreciated. Here below the main suggestions for improvements:

- An example of who are the different "user profiles" accessing the dashboard and their rights would have been useful.
- As for data ingestion, some information are missing for some countries in the sources used. In case information is available in local sources or publications and could be complimented then a brief explanation should be provided on the ingestion page.
- It would be useful to have a way to know the meaning of each country's code.

For one of the respondents the PoC was too basic and not sufficiently developed.

1.3 Validation workshop

The validation workshop took place on September the 9th: 39 persons participated, including EC officers, cadres from the EOSC Association, representatives of several national initiatives, and members of the EOSC Steering Board subgroup on indicators.

The aims of the workshop were to present the final version of the PoC to the community, gather feedback but, especially, delineate possible future steps for on EOSC readiness dashboard. Beside this, the team presented all the work done in terms of requirements and data analysis too. And summarized the main functionalities of the PoC before a live demo.

The main functionalities of the platform we presented were:

- Harvest information from trusted (open) data sources automatically (via API)
- Possibility to upload data manually
- Transparency: data source (person in charge) and date of update visible to admin
- European overview contextualised with country-specific statistics
- Dedicated country page with qualitative and quantitative information

The second part of the validation was interactive with comments from the audience triggered by questions proposed through Sli.do.

We asked what features should be added: answers are reported here after:

- If data is available in separate resources, be able to compare them, in one view
- Possibility to download datasets (actual already available but probably not sufficiently visible)
- Map view visualisation
- A public view (no login)
- Possibility to toggle between absolute numbers and percentages
- Comparisons "per capita" data
- Is the possibility for corrections implemented (even after months?)
- Add some simple tools to analyse data, like main graph divided by context graph, or 2d map of main graph vs context
- Careful selection of meaningful indicators, depends on data availability cross countries
- Quality of the data - to judge validity
- Information on data validation (who did validate them)
- Indication of trustworthiness (e.g., official source through API = 100%)

Out of 13 answers, four refers to the need of assuring data quality and trustworthiness.

Indeed, *data validation emerged as the main challenge for the next step of dashboard development* (see figure below).

Fig. 4 Answers to the question: In your opinion, what are the main challenges in further developing the dashboard?

With reference to this response, we asked if it should be a data validation/certification process: 50% of participants to this pool answered no but indicated that only government officials or experts appointed by government should be allowed to enter data in the dashboard (if not available through API), while 39% of respondents answered positively, asking a validation by national authorities.

Do you think there should be some kind of certification/validation mechanism for the data to be used in the dashboard?

18

Yes, strong certification by independent authority

0 %

Yes validation by national authority (e.g. ministry)

39 %

No, but data should be provided only by government officials/government - appointed experts

50 %

No, the more data the better

11 %

Fig. 5 Participants' feedback on data validation options

Investigating the relevance of some of the functionalities that emerged during the co-design phase but not yet implemented due to time/resources contains, the following opinions were gathered:

- Time-series visualization of data is important for all respondents' participants (see Fig. 6)
- How to capitalize the data available on international e-Infrastructures users gathered divided opinions, with half of the participants suggesting dedicating a separate section of the dashboard to them, while the other half suggesting to use the data on users of e-Infrastructures (when available) as a proxy of national EOSC maturity (see Fig. 7)
- Adding a "tool" able to map the dashboard usage in order to monitor its usage was considered an interesting addition by 38% of respondents, a "must have" for 25%, useful but not a priority by 25% and not useful by 13% of the respondents (see Fig. 8).
- Contextualize some data considering the "size" of the disciplinary community targeted by adding a discipline-related viewer was considered an interesting addition by 53% of the respondents, useful but not a priority by 40%, a "must have" by 7% and none defined it as non-useful (see Fig. 9).

Would it be important to have a time-serie visualisation of the data to see the changes over time? 22

Fig. 6 Participants' feedback on time-series visualization

In our analysis it emerged that several e-Infrastructures (and related services) are not country specific. How should they be considered in the dashboard? 16

Fig. 7 Participants' feedback on e-infrastructures inclusion in the dashboard

It has been suggested to incorporate in the dashboard a “tool” able to map the dashboard usage in order to monitor its impact. What do you think? 16

Fig. 8 Participants’ feedback on a potential tool for mapping the impact of the dashboard

During the co-design phase it was suggested to contextualize some data considering the “size” of the disciplinary community targeted. Should a discipline-related viewer be added? 15

Fig. 9 Participants’ feedback on contextual data on disciplinary communities

An additional question was related to the possibility to use the EOSC service registry data model as a reference standard for the national registries that are emerging in different EU countries. The EOSC service data model is designed for describing services in the EOSC marketplace and, even if currently, does not allow a country-based analysis, also because many

services registered in the marketplaces are international ones or EU projects providing service to several national communities, adopting it across countries could facilitate data merging and comparison. 38% of respondents asked positively, while 31% said that is only partially possible (see Fig. 10).

Fig. 10 Participants' feedback on usage of EOSC marketplace data model

Finally, we investigated sustainability and governance issues by asking whether the EOSC Association should oversee further developing and managing a similar dashboard, or whether others should be in charge. None of the respondents indicate another organisation as an alternative; 53% indicated that the EOSC association should be in charge of a readiness platform as an output of the EOSC-Future project and 33% suggested having the EOSC Association in charge of it right now. During the conversation emerged from these questions we shared with the audience that exchanges and collaboration are undergoing, and that EOSC-Future is working on the requirements of an EOSC readiness dashboard that will take in due consideration the results of this PoC and further work on it.

Should EOSC Association be in charge of further developing and managing a similar dashboard? 15

Yes, right now

Yes, at the end of EOSC Future that can further develop this concept

Don't know

No, another organisation should be in charge

Fig. 11 participants' feedback on role of EOS association in further developing the dashboard

Below the general feedback gathered at the end of the validation workshop, in the form of a Tweet.

- Thanks, great workshop! After validation of data sources and selection of the most meaningful indicators, this will be the basis for a great visualisation tool that can be used for advocacy.
- Great idea, but the quality of some data (esp. OpenAIRE Monitor) is disputable.
- Useful effort--Converge necessary with other monitoring efforts! Data sources and their validation are key.
- The workshop demonstrated that measuring the progress of Open Science is a tricky business! But taking steps to monitor what is happening is brave.
- The PoC is an interesting base for EOSC readiness, but it shows how important reliable data sources are, yet again ;-)
- Very important progress for open science! User friendly visualisation is important and can help identify needs and incentivise progress.
- The concept of EOSC readiness should have been distributed a week in advance before the workshop. This way you will get a half digested, half-thought opinions.
- Great start for a dashboard -- should be used by EOSC Future to be developed further.
- Very interesting and useful tool

2.PoC technical and functional description

The EOSC Readiness dashboard was built integrating 5 main logic blocks which are responsible for carrying out the operations necessary to retrieve, manage and analyze the data and present the results to the analyst. The blocks are:

- Sources: groups the possible input data sources (APIs, static files)
- Ingestion and Transformation: data extraction from sources, collection, alignment and transformation into a more suitable form
- Storage: fast data storage and retrieval
- Processing: KPI calculation and data analysis through statistical techniques
- Data Visualization: display of data to users in an aggregate and detailed manner

Fig. 12PoC technical and functional description

The architecture set up to build the platform makes use of a microservice segmentation of the logical blocks described above. Using containerization with Docker, each service is deployed on a different and separate container that communicates with the other to manage the data.

Fig. 13 Technological components of the PoC

The ingestion pipeline and the connectors were built using Python in combination with Redis Queue, which took care of the queue management and the correct ingestion pipeline timing.

The storage was built using a Clickhouse database, which was chosen for its speed and the possibility to perform actions on the data to enable real-time analytics.

Processing is also performed using Python scripts. For each source type introduced into the platform, specific connectors and elaboration scripts were written.

Through the platform the authorized users can monitor the processing flow (on the Monitoring area of the platform) and receive information about the elaboration queue of their requests. The Flask library was used to develop the endpoints needed to start python tasks with http requests.

Once the analysis is complete, the data is made available through clickhouse to the Grafana visualization engine. The graphs built with Grafana are then automatically updated alongside the data on the database.

On top of these components, a graphic interface was built using the Processwire CMS and a Postgres database. Through the CMS it is possible to manage and define users, roles, indicators, context data and choose which graphs to match and show to the users. Acting also as a backend interface, the CMS enables the possibility to add new indicators and sources whenever needed.

The collected data is also made available for download through the graphical frontend below its graphical representation on the Visualization area of the platform.

2.1 Software versions

The following software versions were used in the PoC

Software	Version
Docker	
Python	3.8
Redis Queue	5.0.13
Clickhouse	21.0
Grafana	8.0.2
Processwire	3.0.165
Postgres	13.0

Tab. 2 Softwares used and related versions

Python libraries

The following are the main python libraries used to perform ingestion and elaboration on data.

Library	Version
certifi	2021.5.30
charset-normalizer	2.0.3
country-converter	0.7.3
idna	3.2
numpy	1.21.1
pandahouse	0.2.7
pandas	1.3.1
python-dateutil	2.8.2

pytz	2021.1
requests	2.26.0
schedule	1.1.0
six	1.16.0
toolz	0.11.1
urllib3	1.26.6
docker	5.0.0
Flask	2.0.1
websocket-client	1.0.1

Tab. 3 Python libraries and related versions

2.2 Workflows for the automatic and non-automatic data collection

Automatic data collection

This process refers to the retrieval of data from an API. Once the user sets up the parameters for the ingestion through the graphical interface, the platform adds the specific ingestion task to its queue.

Once the task gets priority in the queue, the Python script that interfaces with the selected API starts downloading the updated data and stores them in the Clickhouse database.

When the process ends, data is made available to the Grafana component, which reads them through a query to the database in order to generate the graphs. The graphs that are embedded in the interface are then automatically updated and presented to the user.

The endpoint set up for the PoC to retrieve OpenAire data is: <https://services.openaire.eu/stats-tool/raw>

Non-automatic data collection

This process refers to the retrieval of data from a CSV uploaded by the user to the platform.

Once the user sets up the parameters for the ingestion through the graphical interface, he must also upload a CSV file containing the data. The file must adhere to the data structure set up for the specific indicator that is being updated. Once the file is uploaded, the platform adds the specific ingestion task to its queue. Once the task gets priority in the queue, the Python script reads through the CSV and stores the data in the Clickhouse database.

When the process ends, data is made available to the Grafana component, which reads them through a query to the database in order to generate the graphs. The graphs that are embedded in the interface are then automatically updated and presented to the user.

The following are the data structure specification for each of the indicators' CSV:

- DESI data - <https://digital-agenda-data.eu/datasets/desi>
 - SERIES
 - CATEGORY
 - CODE
 - VALUE NOTE
 - FLAG
 - COUNTRY
- Education expenditure -
https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=educ_figdp&lang=en
 - TIME
 - GEO
 - INDIC_ED
 - UNIT
 - Value
 - Flag and Footnotes
- Allocated government budget for R&D -
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/gba_nabste/default/table?lang=en
 - DATAFLOW
 - Freq
 - Unit
 - Geo
 - TIME_PERIOD
 - OBS_VALUE OBS_FLAG
- Population -
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/demo_pjan/default/table?lang=en
 - DATAFLOW
 - Freq
 - Unit
 - Age
 - Sex
 - Geo
 - TIME_PERIOD
 - OBS_VALUE OBS_FLAG
- R&D expenditure per country -
https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=rd_p_perslf&lang=en
 - TIME
 - GEO
 - SEX
 - PROF_POS
 - SECTPERF
 - UNIT
 - Value
 - Flag and Footnotes
- Graduates at doctoral level by sex and age groups per 1000 of population aged 25-34 -
https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=educ_uoe_grad06&lang=en
 - TIME

- GEO
- UNIT
- SEX
- AGE
- Value
- Flag and Footnotes
- Population having completed tertiary education age 25-34 -
https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=edat_lfse_03&lang=en
 - GEO
 - TIME
 - SEX
 - AGE
 - UNIT
 - ISCED11
 - Value
 - Flag and Footnotes

2.3 Consideration for future developments

One of the main difficulties encountered during the development was the availability of the APIs to which we needed to connect in order to retrieve the data. Where those APIs were available, it was not always possible to interface directly with them. In some cases, the documentation relating to the interfacing processes was dated, not exhaustive or even not present.

For example, the OpenAire portal showed graphic representations of the data that the API should have exposed, and in order to find the correct endpoints that provided the same data it was necessary to analyze the construction (i.e. the code) of the pages in which these endpoints were used to produce tables or graphs. In the EOSC Pillar case, proceeding with the authorization process we have found bugs that are in the process of being corrected at the time of writing and have prevented us from interface directly with the API.

API	Documentation	Notes
OpenAire	incomplete	The following undocumented API was used in the PoC: https://services.openaire.eu/stats-tool/raw
EOSC Pillar Italy - login API	outdated	It was not possible to get the auth token following the documentation, it was necessary to open a ticket on the issue logger to get one
EOSC Pillar Italy	outdated	It was not possible to log after getting the authorization token, each request resolved with a “500 server error” response

Tab. 4 Data sets contacted via API and comments

With regard to UX/UI design, a stable release of the dashboard could provide the user with the possibility to customize visualization and ingestion parameters depending on user's permissions profile. Read-only users could be enabled to limited visualization setting options such as scales and visualized time range. Admin users will be able to update indicators data, while developers will be able to change reference indicators such as thresholds or country color-code (i.e. fixating the association between countries and colours used in the visualization section).

3. Considerations and recommendations

As clearly emerged in section 2, data availability and data trustworthiness are key elements in further developing an EOSC readiness dashboard. We must acknowledge that, at the present stage, this are two major challenges for the full implementation of a dashboard but, nevertheless the approach followed in the PoC is considered as viable and interesting by most of the stakeholders meet during the project. Moreover, several national and international organisations are working on indicators definition and data repository development, first of all national registries for EOSC services and training.

Therefore, we divide our recommendations in two groups: to be considered in the short term and to be considered to have a more efficient dashboard in the long period.

Short term recommendations

- Considering that most data- in many countries - will need to be inserted manually, due to lack of Open Data repositories or due to interoperability issues, it is important to develop a form for data entry by selecting a limited number of information to be requested.
- For selecting the data to be requested in the form, it is necessary to start by analysing the data that are available across most countries. The list of indicators developed by the landscaping task force could be a starting point, but other tools (such as the country sheet developed by the Landscaping Working Group, or the questionnaire developed by the EOSC-Pillar project in their landscape analysis) should be considered too in order to develop a sort of lowest common denominator of available data.
- Only use data that are available for at least 10 EU countries (possibly different in terms of EOSC maturity, country dimensions and typology of research institutions: centralised vs decentralized), otherwise the users will find the dashboard not sufficiently useful.
- A shared decision of whom (typology of stakeholder) should enter the data - at country level - in this first phase of development of the platform, must be reached. It is important to consider that data are not going to be entered by a single person as indicators refers to different Open Science-related aspects (policies, infrastructures, training, etc) so more than one person should be selected for each country. It is mandatory that the different persons providing data for a specific country collaborate all together to assure alignment among different data providers at country level. Moreover, definition of role and, in case

of need, “hierarchy” among data providers should be clearly defined upfront data provision.

- The persons in charge of data entry at country level must be clearly recognised in the platform, at least by the platform manager, but - in a logic of transparency - this should be possible also for general users. The persons in charge of data entry should be recognisable also in terms of organisation of belonging/affiliation.
- Data source and data of upload is visible in the PoC for each of the selected indicators and it is crucial that this remain as a key functionality of the dashboard.
- The PoC clearly showed that development of an EOSC readiness platform is a *socio-technical* task and, if from a technological point of view, there are various efficient Open Source solutions (such as the ones used in the PoC), the “social” aspects of the work are more complex and demanding. More specifically, the work on indicator selection, data availability analysis, data quality assurance, data elaboration, data entry governance design, data visualisation and user interphase design ask for the active engagement of social scientists in the development team. Indeed, experts of sociology of science and innovation, co-design and participatory processes and statisticians should be part of such a team.

Long terms recommendations

- Additional data visualisation option should be added, such as map-based graphs.
- The list of contextual data should be increased and, ideally, each indicator should be matched with one or more contextual indicators for better interpreting it.
- Align the national registry among them and with the EOSC marketplace data model.
- Add a feature able to map the usage of the dashboard (number of users, number of downloads or similar).
- Consider the possibility of having an international body (it could be the EOSC association) running a yearly data collection survey instead of having different persons in each EU country entering data in the dashboard. The approach of the NREN compendium (<https://compendium.geant.org/#!/>) carried out by Géant can be taken as a reference in this sense.
- Alternatively, persons in charge of data entry in the dashboard should be:
 - Selected by national authorities
 - Properly trained in using the dashboard
 - Provided with clear definitions for each of the indicators used in the dashboard and supported in selecting the most appropriate data source at national level. A clear list of requirements should be developed to support data source selection.
 - Engaging national statistical offices and appoint them to act as data providers could be an alternative option too.

- In case indicators need to be dropped/added or slightly changed it is recommended to do these changes gradually, by keeping part of the indicators stable to assure the possibility to visualize progress over time.
- A content management system should be added to enrich the country pages, allowing the possibility to add free text summarizing the country situation in terms of EOSC readiness and making available for download studies and reports. The free text should in any case be based on a common template and on a agreed style in order to support comparability and re-use of information.

Additional consideration

Scalability

Although the PoC currently works with low numbers in terms of users and requests for data updates, it was decided from the beginning to think of the platform architecture as scalable and potentially usable even in cases of high load through the use of queues. The Cloud infrastructure allows the PoC to have very high uptime and to scale quickly where necessary, based on the load the platform is facing.

The split of the functionalities into microservices, managed by Docker containers, allows to promptly intervene on the various components and possibly update or modify only those that need an update, without affecting the rest of the platform. The interoperability layers developed have been created taking into account the most widespread and current standards (API RESTful, JSON, CSV). OpenSource software solutions were preferred, guaranteeing stability in terms of security, since they are constantly updated by the communities that support them.

In terms of future enhancements, the platform could be further automated to allow users to add additional endpoints (as long as they use standardized communication systems). The triggering of ingestion could also be automated and made periodic without requiring the intervention of an operator, so that the data is automatically and periodically updated. The part relating to the graphical interface could be improved in terms of UX / UI once developing farther the platform for a public release, dedicating the needed time to co-design it with the actual users.

Annex 1 - PoC user manual

Login

Authorized users could login from the home page with their credentials. Once logged in, they can navigate the portal using the main tabs situated on top of the page.

The screenshot shows the 'EOSC Readiness dashboard' login interface. At the top right, there is a 'guest' dropdown menu. Below the navigation bar, the 'INGESTION' tab is active. The login form is centered and includes a 'User' field with the text 'admin', a 'Password' field with masked characters, and a 'Login' button. The footer contains the text 'Copyright 2021 © All Rights Reserved.'

Ingestion

In the ingestion tab, the user can setup the data update. If the Source type is an API, the user will only select the country and the indicator. If the Source type is a CSV, the user will also need to upload a file and indicate the Data Source. In order to use the correct data structure, the user could download beforehand the last valid file used or navigate the open data source for the selected indicator.

EOSC Readiness dashboard

admin-italy

INGESTION MONITORING VISUALIZATION

Country
Italy

Indicator *
Population with tertiary education

File *
• Scegli file Nessun file selezionato

Data source *

Available open data source for this indicator: https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=edat_lfse_03&lang=en

Last valid file uploaded (use as model file): https://collector-garr.eosc-rm.catchy.buzz/site/assets/files/1101/edat_lfse_03_1_data.csv

Submit

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Monitoring

In the monitoring page the user could see all the ingestion task that are ended or in progress. Using the textbox, the user could also filter the list with a full-text search.

EOSC Readiness dashboard

admin-italy

INGESTION MONITORING VISUALIZATION

27/07/2021 14:	Q
Country: Number of Open Access Repositories in Europe - API - JSON Source: https://osobservatory.openaire.eu/ Updated on: 27/07/2021 14:44:54 Status: elaborato by: admin	
Country: Number of Open Access Repositories in Europe - API - JSON Source: https://osobservatory.openaire.eu/ Updated on: 27/07/2021 14:10:07 Status: elaborato by: admin	
Country: Number of Open Access Datasets in Europe - API - JSON Source: https://osobservatory.openaire.eu/ Updated on: 27/07/2021 14:09:37 Status: elaborato by: admin	

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Visualization

The main Visualization page shows the general indicators. To view an indicator the user must choose it from the dropdown menu. The original data could be downloaded using the icon on the bottom right of each graph. The source of the data is available at the link below the graph.

The Indicators section contains EOSC readiness indicators for all EU28 countries. The red line fixated in each histogram is visualized with the mere purpose of giving an idea about how a readiness threshold could be visualized. As stated above, a stable release of the dashboard could provide developer/user with the possibility to customize visualization parameters such as thresholds levels or country color-code (i.e. fixating the association between countries and colours used in the visualization section).

The context data section provides the user with the possibility to visualize some indicators regarding socio-economic characteristic of the Country useful as a context frame reference.

[EOSC Readiness dashboard](#)

In the Country page, the user could select context data and indicator data from the dropdown and download the original data from the icon on the bottom right of the graph.

EOSC Readiness dashboard

admin-italy

The user can interact with the provided graphs simply placing the mouse over the data to be analyzed. The user can also select a specific range of the graph in order to zoom in-out and select a specific time range.

Portugal Detail Page

Portugal Detail Page

Annex 2 - Estimation of the effort needed to implement annual monitoring at country level.

If the data at a country level are available as Open Data and through API, the time and cost for annual update is practically zero as it is done automatically by the dashboard with few clicks by the operators. For those data that are not available as API it is not possible to provide an overall estimation as the process to be followed changes from country to country according to data availability and governance process identified but, once the process will be standardized across Europe, it should request two-three working days considering the current amount of indicators considered.

In terms of compliance with standards and technical updates, all components are OSS and easy to update so two-three days of work on an early base seems a fair estimation.